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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF EFFICACY OF INTESTINAL
ANASTOMOSIS SUTURED IN SINGLE LAYER VERSUS TWO
LAYER****¹Dr. Muhammad Tanveer Sajid, ²Dr. Rana Shakeel Ahmed, ³Dr. Nazish Syed**¹Latin American School of Medicine, Cuba

Sargodha Medical College, Sargodha

³Baqai Medical University, Karachi**Abstract:**

Objective: To evaluate the safety of an extra mucosal intestinal anastomosis in a single layer compared to conventional double-layer intestinal anastomosis.

Study design: A case control study.

Configuration and Duration: In the Surgical Unit II of Services Hospital Lahore for six months duration from January 2018 to June 2018.

Methodology: All patients needs intestinal anastomosis were selected. The two groups of patients were made. In A group, an extra-mucosal interrupted anastomosis of a single layer was performed with vicryl 2/0, while in group B, with vicryl 2/0 a conventional double-layered anastomosis was done. The results of the two techniques were compared in terms of morbidity, mortality and cost-effectiveness.

Results: Ninety patients were included in the study (42 in group A and 48 in group B). The mean age of the group A was 37.5 and the B group was 40.2 years, respectively. Entero-colostomy, colo-colostomy and Entero-enterostomy were done in 10(23.8%), 2(4.7%) and 30(71.4%) patients in-group A and 10(20.8%), 3(6.3%) and 35(72.9%) patients in group B respectively. Two patients (4.7%) in Group A and four patients (8.3%) in group B developed anastomotic leaks with a general mortality rate of 0% and 4.1% in group B.

Conclusion: Single layer interrupted extra mucosal intestinal can be formed in less time with a less complication compared to the two-layer technique. Surgical training program can be entered safely in this regard.

Key Words: Anastomosis, Fugue, monolayer interruption, morbidity and mortality.

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INTRODUCTION:

The basic principles of intestinal anastomosis were established more than 100 years ago and have undergone changes over time. In 1926, Lembert described a suture technique called serous suture. Senn described a two-layer technique anastomosis, while Halsted proposed a single layered anastomosis. The techniques are designed at different times, but there is no single internationally accepted technique. The objections to double-layer anastomosis are that in most cases they do not confront clean serous surfaces and produce a large amount of ischemic tissue that increases the likelihood of leakage within the seam line. An excess of excessive inversion causes decrease diameter of lumen. In contrast, the monolayer anastomosis causes the possibility of the least damage to the submucosal vascular plexus and the most powerful subcutaneous layer and full addition of the tissue approximation. This prospective comparative study was performed to assess the safety of a single-layer interrupted extra-mucosal technique.

METHODOLOGY:

This prospective study was held in the Surgical Unit II of Services Hospital Lahore for six months

duration from January 2018 to June 2018. All patients requiring intestinal anastomosis were included, but those who wanted anastomosis in the stomach, duodenum and rectum were included. Patients were randomized to one or two layer techniques. Ninety patients were included in this study. The group A divided further into A and B into two groups, 42 patients were included and they were treated with an extra-mucosal anastomosis of a single layer technique with vicryl 2/0. In group B, 48 patients underwent conventional double layer anastomosis with vicryl 2/0. All patients were operated by the same group of surgeons and elderly residents supported by an assistant surgeon. The same group (Cefotaxime and Metronidazole) antibiotics were used for 5 days in both groups. The results were compared in terms of morbidity, mortality and cost effectiveness after two techniques.

RESULTS:

Group A (single coat) and group B (double coat) were matched in the same way as age, gender, diagnosis and location of anastomosis (Table I).

Table I. Size of abscess and treatment

	Group A (One Layer)	Group B (Two Layer)
Number of Anastomosis	42	48
Age Years	37	40
Sex Male, Female	30/12	32/16
Diagnosis		
Trauma RTA/Gunshot	9	8
Inflammatory (T.B)	16	22
Malignancy (Cancer)	4	6
Ileostomy Closure	11	9
Colostomy Closure	2	3
Location		
Enterocenterostomy	30	35
Enterocolostomy	10	10
Colocolostomy	2	3

The mean age for group A was 37.5 (16-68) and for group B it was 40 year (range 15-69). The gender distribution was 30 men and 12 women in group A, 32 men and 16 women in group B. In our study, anastomotic leak was detected in 6 patients (8.9%). In Group A, leakage occurred in two patients, responded well to conservative treatment, while in group B, leakage occurred in four patients; by sepsis). One patient in group B died due to intra-abdominal abscess, sepsis and multiorgan failure (Table II).

Table II. Post-operative complications

Complications	Group A (n=42)	Group B (n=48)
Wound Infection	3(7.1%)	5(10.4%)
Wound Dehiscence	—	3(6.2%)
Anastomotic Leaks	2(4.7%)	4(8.3%)
Intra Abdominal Abscesses	2(4.7%)	3(6.2%)

The duration of hospitalization was 8.2 days for group A and 10.5 days for group B. There was no mortality in Group A and two patients (4.1%) died due to complications.

DISCUSSION:

This study evaluated the efficacy and safety of one and two-fold anastomosis after intestinal resection. In general, a conventional two-layer technique is applied, but this leads to excessive inversion in the mucosa, may cause narrowing of the lumen and may cause ischemia of the anastomosis site. To overcome this problem, a suture technique that cuts the extra mucosa has been tried. It has the advantage of good resistance to serous surfaces without luminal constriction and less damage to the submucosal vascular plexus. In this study, anastomotic leakage in group A was 4.7%. It is consistent with other studies showing leakage in the 1.3 to 7.7% range. Among the group B, this study shows that there is an anastomotic leak at around 8.3%, which is considerably higher than the rate described in the literature. The mortality rate in Group A is 0% and in Group B it is 4.1%. Once again, it is consistent with those described in the literature. The safety and minimal complications of the extra-mucosal anastomosis of a single layer on other anastomotic techniques have been appreciated by an audit published in the BJS in 1991.

CONCLUSION:

Single-layered anastomosis of the mucosa is one of the promising techniques with insignificant complications and remarkable advantages.

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